

Quantum chemical study of the structures, stability and vibrational spectra of the nitrous acid complexes with B₂O₂ and C₂N₂ molecules

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Abstract : *Ab initio* calculations at the SCF and MP2 levels with 6-311G basis set have been used to investigate the structures, stability and vibrational spectra of the binary complexes B₂O₂-HONO(*trans*) and B₂O₂-HONO(*cis*) along with complexes of C₂N₂-HONO(*trans*) and C₂N₂-HONO(*cis*). Full geometry optimization was made for the complexes studied here. It was established that the complex B₂O₂-HONO(*trans*) is more stable by 2.40 kcal/mol than the complex B₂O₂-HONO(*cis*) and C₂N₂-HONO(*trans*) is more stable by 2.48 kcal/mol than C₂N₂-HONO(*cis*). The accuracy of the *ab initio* calculations have been estimated by comparison between the predicted values of the vibrational characteristics (frequencies and infrared intensities) and the available experimental data. It was established that the molecules, used in the present work, are well correlated. The changes in the vibrational frequencies of B₂O₂, C₂N₂ and *trans*, *cis*-nitrous acid upon formation of hydrogen bond respectively showed that the complexes B₂O₂-HONO(*trans*) and B₂O₂-HONO(*cis*) have geometry in which the OH group interacts with B₂O₂ molecules forming a single hydrogen bond. Similar study was also observed for C₂N₂ and HONO complexes.

Keywords : Complexes, B₂O₂, MP2 method, nitrous acid, C₂N₂.

Introduction

Nitrous acid, one of the smallest molecule, plays a major role in atmospheric chemistry and exhibits *cis-trans* conformational equilibrium. The studies of nitrous acid complexes with various bases B-HONO in low temperature matrices have shown that nitrous acid complexes in which OH group acts as a proton donor have comparable strength to the corresponding complexes of hydrogen halides, B-HX with the same bases^{1,2}. The classification of the structure and stability of the hydrogen bonded complexes of nitrous acid with various atmospheric bases is very important in atmospheric chemistry. Since it is difficult to do direct measurement of the rate and mechanism of heterogeneous reactions on the surface or in liquid droplets under the condition of Antarctic stratosphere, the computer simulations of such reactions are very useful for the classification of the structure and stability of the hydrogen bonded complexes important for atmospheric chemistry³⁻¹⁰. The *cis-trans*

isomerism of nitrous acid was the first reported instance of an infrared stereo chemical reaction^{11,12}. It is an unstable molecule in the vapor phase and exists in the complex equilibrium with the products of its decomposition. Despite these difficulties the low resolution IR^{13,14} and high resolution FTIR¹⁵⁻¹⁸ and laser infrared spectra¹⁹⁻²² of *cis-trans* HONO have been extensively studied. The hydrogen bonded complexes of nitrous acid with various molecules viz. CH₄²³, C₂H₂²⁴, CO, N₂¹ have been reported. Furthermore, weakly bound molecular dimers have been extensively investigated in the gas phase by radio frequency, microwave and high resolution infrared spectroscopy²⁵. The object of the present study are the binary complexes B₂O₂-HONO (*trans*) (1A) and B₂O₂-HONO (*cis*) (1B). The complex formation of C₂N₂-HONO (*trans*) (2A) and C₂N₂-HONO (*cis*) (2B) have also been the subject of the present investigation for comparison since both B₂O₂ and C₂N₂ are isoelectronic. Here we wish to furnish some information regarding B₂O₂ molecule.

Table 1. Optimized geometries for free and complexed HONO and B₂O₂ molecule, obtained from HF/6-311G calculations

Parameters	<i>trans</i> -HONO			<i>cis</i> -HONO		
	Monomer	Complex	Δ	Monomer	Complex	Δ
Bond length (Å)						
<i>r</i> (O ₁ N ₂)	1.175	1.228	0.053	1.186 (1.153)	1.19	0.004
<i>r</i> (N ₂ O ₃)	1.375	1.360	-0.015	1.358 (1.304)	1.347	-0.011
<i>r</i> (O ₃ H ₄)	0.949	0.954	0.005	0.960	0.964	0.004
<i>r</i> (H ₄ ⋯O ₅)		1.927			1.8500	
<i>r</i> (O ₅ B ₆)	1.190 (1.182)	1.199	0.009	-	1.192	
<i>r</i> (B ₆ B ₇)	1.640 (1.668)	1.643	0.003	-	1.644	
<i>r</i> (B ₇ O ₈)	1.190	1.189	-0.001	-	1.188	
Angles (°)						
O ₁ -N ₂ -O ₃	111.8	110.9	-0.9	113.9	114.4	0.5
N ₂ -O ₃ -H ₄	108.4	107.9	-0.5	112.1	113.8	1.7
O ₃ -H ₄ ⋯O ₅	-	154.8		-	171.3	
H ₄ O⋯B ₆		137.4			169.8	

The values in parentheses are experimental and have been taken from Ref. 29.

^aSee Figure for numbered atoms.

This molecule in the gaseous phase was first reported²⁶ when a mixture of boron and B₂O₃ was assumed to have linear symmetric structure O=B-B=O isoelectronic to cyanogens. Later on, other non-linear structure were proposed on the basis of bond energy considerations. The topologies of these structures were examined by *ab initio* calculations at the lower basis set level and by semi empirical methods²⁷ followed by the photoelectron spectra to determine the most stable structure of B₂O₂²⁸. The B₂O₂ molecule, being very interesting, from the point of view of atmospheric chemistry and has resemblance with C₂N₂ on electronic level, we have chosen to investigate

the hydrogen bond complexation with nitrous acid. In the previous study we carried out the theoretical calculations at SCF and DFT tends for hydrogen halide (HX)-B₂O₂ binary complexes²⁹.

Computational details :

All calculations were performed within the framework of the *ab initio* and DFT approach using HYPERCHEM 2003 package of computer code³⁰. Electron correlation was considered via the Moller-Plesset perturbation theory^{31,32} to the second order including explicitly all electrons. The structures of the isolated monomers,

Table 2. Energetics and electronic parameters for free and complexed HONO (*trans* and *cis*) and B₂O₂ obtained from HF/6-311G calculations

Parameters	HONO- <i>cis</i>	HONO- <i>trans</i>	B ₂ O ₂	HONO-B ₂ O ₂ - <i>cis</i>	HONO-B ₂ O ₂ - <i>trans</i>
B.E. (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-128378.94	-128379.73	-124971.84	-253358.78	-253361.97
μ (Debye)	1.825	2.913	0.0	3.151	3.357
HOMO (eV)	-13.2118	-12.6340	-14.8974	-12.4918	-12.5381
LUMO (eV)	1.9851	2.2105	1.1076	0.5102	0.5957
μΔ _{<i>cis</i>}	1.326D				
μΔ _{<i>trans</i>}	0.444D				
E _{<i>trans</i>} H-bond	-10.40				
E _{<i>cis</i>} H-bond	-8.00				

Table 3. Mulliken charges (q_i) for free and complexed HONO (*trans* and *cis*) and B_2O_2 obtained from HF/6-311G calculations

Sl. no. ^a	Atom	<i>trans</i> -HONO			<i>cis</i> -HONO		
		Monomer	Complex	Δq_i^a	Monomer	Complex	Δq_i
1.	O	-0.269	-0.22	0.049	-0.336	-0.356	-0.02
2.	N	0.399	0.306	-0.093	0.473	0.442	-0.031
3.	O	-0.554	0.568	1.122	-0.544	-0.576	-0.32
4.	H	0.425	0.468	0.043	0.407	0.458	0.051
5.	O	-0.452	0.540	0.992	-0.452	-0.518	-0.066
6.	B	0.452	0.507	0.055	0.452	0.482	0.03
7.	B	0.452	0.485	0.033	0.452	0.499	0.047
8.	O	-0.452	-0.437	0.006	-0.452	-0.434	0.018

^a $\Delta q_i = q_i^{\text{complex}} - q_i^{\text{monomer}}$.

HONO, B_2O_2 and C_2N_2 and their complexes were fully optimized by using the 6-311G basis set^{33,34}. Vibrational frequencies and intensities were computed both for the monomers and for the complexes.

Results and discussion

Structure and stability :

In the study of structure and stability of molecular complexes, it is essential to assess the accuracy with which the computational procedure reproduces the essential properties of the individual subunits. The calculated data for HONO, B_2O_2 and their *cis-trans*

complexes are reported in Table I along with available experimental data. Comparison of calculated and experimental values of geometrical parameters clearly shows that the theoretical approach used in this study well correlates with the experimental data. The first step, in the present work, was to establish the most stable structure of the complexes between B_2O_2 and HONO (*trans* and *cis*) by *ab initio* calculation at SCF level with 6-311G basis set. Full geometry optimization has been performed for the monomers and complexes studied. The accuracy for energy minimization was established with convergence limit 0.01 kcal/Å and Polak-Rieberger

Table 4. Optimized geometries for free and complexed HONO and C_2N_2 molecule, obtained from HF/6-311G calculations

Parameters ^a	<i>trans</i> -HONO			<i>cis</i> -HONO		
	Monomer	Complex	Δ	Monomer	Complex	Δ
Bond length (Å)						
$r(O_1N_2)$	1.175	1.179	0.004	1.186	1.189	0.003
$r(N_2O_3)$	1.375	1.361	-0.014	1.358	1.350	-0.008
$r(O_3H_4)$	0.949	0.952	0.003	0.960	0.982	0.022
$r(H_4 \cdots N_5)$	-	2.029	-	-	2.146	-
$r(N_5C_6)$	1.139	1.137	-0.002	1.139	1.138	-0.001
$r(C_6C_7)$	1.378	1.378	0.000	1.378	1.377	-0.001
$r(C_7N_8)$	1.139	1.138	-0.001	1.139	1.139	0.0
Angles (°)						
$O_1-N_2-O_3$	111.8	112.1	0.3	113.9	114.3	0.4
$N_2-O_3-H_4$	108.4	109.4	1.0	112.1	113.2	1.1
$O_3-H_4 \cdots N_5$	-	173.8	-	-	165.9	-
$H_4-N_5 \cdots C_6$	-	179.3	-	-	146.2	-

algorithm has been used for fast and accurate computation. Our aim was to select the most stable structure for the complexes B_2O_2 -HONO(*trans*) (**1A**) and B_2O_2 -HONO(*cis*) (**1B**). In Fig. 1 and Tables 1–3 are shown the structures, optimum values of the total energy, dipole moment, HOMO-LUMO frontier orbitals and optimized structural parameters for the hydrogen bonded complexes **1A** and **1B**. As can be seen from the results of the binding energy in Table 3, the complex B_2O_2 -HONO(*trans*) (**1A**) is more stable than B_2O_2 -HONO(*cis*) (**1B**). The calculated structural parameters for the monomers (HONO-*trans*, HONO-*cis* and B_2O_2) are compared with the corresponding parameters for the complexes **1A** and **1B**. The changes in the structural parameters from monomers to complexes are defined. It is seen that bond length and angles for the binary complexes are slightly perturbed from their values

in the monomers (Table 1). The more sensitive to the complexation are the structural parameters on HONO-*trans*. The N_2 - O_3 bond is shorter upon formation of the hydrogen bond by 0.015 Å while the bond O_3 - H_4 is lengthened in the complex by 0.005 Å, the corresponding changes for the HONO-*cis* are smaller in comparison. Furthermore, nitrous acid acts as a proton donor and B_2O_2 as proton acceptor, so during complexation of the two monomers, there is smaller increase in the dipole moment value hence less polarization of HONO-*trans*- B_2O_2 complex than HONO-*cis*- B_2O_2 complex. This also confirms the strong H-bonding in the *trans*-complex. The calculated value of hydrogen bond energy for the *trans*-complex is more than 2.40 kcal/mol, than *cis*-complex (Table 3). According to frontier orbital theory, the stability of the binary complex depends on the upper shift of the HOMO energy level, larger the shift lesser is the stability (ionization potential) with respect to their corresponding monomers. It can be seen from results (Table 3), there is larger shift in the ionization energy of *cis*-complex (**1B**) by 0.72 eV than *trans*-complex.

In order to investigate the net atomic charge distribution of monomers (HONO-*trans*, HONO-*cis* and B_2O_2) upon hydrogen bonding, the atomic charges (q_i) for the monomers and for the complexes **1A** and **1B** have been calculated from HF/6-311G calculations using the Mulliken population analysis. The changes in the atomic charges (Δq_i) from the monomers to complexes have been estimated (see Table 3). The results show that the

Table 5. Mulliken charges (q_i) for free and complexed HONO (*trans* and *cis*) and C_2N_2 obtained from HF/6-311G calculations

Sl. no.	Atom	<i>trans</i> -HONO			<i>cis</i> -HONO		
		Monomer	Complex	Δq_i^a	Monomer	Complex	Δq_i
1.	O	-0.269	-0.295	-0.026	-0.336	-0.340	-0.004
2.	N	0.399	0.388	-0.011	0.473	0.444	-0.029
3.	O	-0.554	-0.569	-0.015	-0.544	-0.555	-0.011
4.	H	0.425	0.453	0.028	0.407	0.438	0.031
5.	N	-0.057	-0.117	-0.060	-0.057	-0.129	-0.072
6.	C	0.057	0.125	0.068	0.057	0.126	0.069
7.	C	0.057	0.051	-0.006	0.057	0.062	0.005
8.	N	-0.057	-0.037	0.020	-0.057	-0.045	-0.012

$$^a \Delta q_i = q_i^{\text{complex}} - q_i^{\text{monomer}}$$

Table 6. Energetics and electronic parameters for free and complexed HONO (*trans* and *cis*) and C₂N₂ obtained from HF/6-311G calculations

Parameters	HONO- <i>trans</i>	HONO- <i>cis</i>	C ₂ N ₂	HONO-C ₂ N ₂ - <i>trans</i>	HONO-C ₂ N ₂ - <i>cis</i>
B.E. (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-128379.73	-128378.94	-115801.81	-244186.94	-244183.67
μ (Debye)	2.913	1.825	0.003	4.194	2.484
HOMO (eV)	-12.6340	-13.2118	-13.7303	-12.1357	-12.9160
LUMO (eV)	2.2105	1.9851	1.7781	1.0406	1.2530
μΔ _{<i>cis</i>}	0.659				
μΔ _{<i>trans</i>}	1.281				
E _{H-bond} ^{<i>trans</i>}	-2.92				
E _{H-bond} ^{<i>cis</i>}	-5.40				

negativity of O₃ and O₅ increases significantly in the complex and positivity of hydrogen also increases significantly. The charges on nitrogen atom in *trans*-complex show larger shift than in *cis*-complex. Hence the hydrogen bonding formation show that O₃, N₂ and O₆ acts as an acceptor of electronic charge and the H-atom release electronic charge. The charge transfer upon hydrogen bonding for HONO(*trans*)-B₂O₂ is more significant than for HONO(*cis*)-B₂O₂.

Since, C₂N₂ (cyanogen) being isoelectronic to B₂O₂, hence the complexation of HONO with this molecule have also been studied. This has been done to compare the structures and stability with hydrogen-bonded complexes of B₂O₂. The geometrical parameters of the HONO (*trans* and *cis*), C₂N₂ and their respective complexes have been reported in Table 4. It can be seen from the results that O₂H₁ bond in HONO(*cis*)-C₂N₂ complex increases by 0.02 Å in comparison to HONO-*cis* monomer, during H-bond formation and more in HONO(*trans*)-C₂N₂ complex by 0.03 Å. Similarly the atomic charge distribution is also altered during complexation of HONO (*cis*, *trans*) with C₂N₂ molecule (Table 5). The energetic and electronic parameters are shown in Table 6. One can observe from the results that the strong H-bonded complex is more pronounced in HONO-*trans* by 1.48 kcal/mol than HONO-*cis*. The -ve atomic charges on O₃ and N₅ atoms increase with respect to their monomers on complexation, but it is more, in the case of HONO(*trans*)-C₂N₂ than HONO(*cis*)-C₂N₂ complex. It further shows that the charge redistribution leads to more stronger H-bond formation in *trans*-form than *cis*-form of HONO.

Vibrational spectra :

The prediction of the vibrational characteristic (vibrational frequencies and intensities) of the hydrogen bonded system by *ab initio* calculations at different levels^{37,38} has become widely employed, in order to, elucidate the influence of the hydrogen bonding, on the vibrational spectra of the monomers forming a complex. In the hydrogen bonded system, the geometrical symmetry of the monomers often changes under perturbation³⁹. The vibrational mixing derived by a perturbation approach, is the counterpart of the orbital mixing. The vibrational frequencies and infrared intensities for free monomers (HONO-*trans*, HONO-*cis*, B₂O₂ and C₂N₂) and their binary complexes **1A**, **1B**, **2A** and **2B** (see Fig. 1) have been predicted by *ab initio* calculations at the SCF and MP2 levels with 6-311G basis set (Tables 7-11).

The first step in the study is to predict the vibrational characteristic for monomers. The predicted values of vibrational frequencies and intensities are compared with the available experimental data (see Table 7). The purpose is to establish the accuracy of the calculations used in the study and to define the "optimal" scale factors for each vibration from the ratio $v_{\text{exp}}/v_{\text{cal}}$. The concept has been proposed by Destexbe *et al.*⁴⁰ in order to obtain an estimation of the anharmonicity of the modes in H-bonded H₂O with pyridine. This procedure could only be applied for modes which are experimentally accessible in the spectral region. In the present study the average "optimal"

Table 7. Experimental and calculated vibrational frequencies (cm⁻¹) for HONO (*trans*), HONO (*cis*) and B₂O₂/C₂N₂ obtained from HF/6-311G and MP2 calculations

Mode	HF	MP2	Expt.
<i>trans</i> -HONO			
ν_1 (O-H stretch)	4058 (117.2)	4038	3572.6/3568.5
ν_2 (N=O stretch)	1889 (121)	1872	1689.1/1688.0
ν_3 (N-OH bend + N-O stretch)	1445 (238)	1431	1265.8/1263.9
ν_4 (N-O stretch)	1007.8 (227.0)	990	800.4
ν_5 (O-N-O bend)	747 (19)	777	796.6
ν_6 (N-OH wagging)	567 (197)	558	549.4/548.2
<i>cis</i> -HONO			
ν_1 (O-H stretch)	3885 (45)	3871	3412.4/3410.7
ν_2 (N=O stretch)	1817 (198)	1795	1634.0/1632.8
ν_3 (N-O-H bend)	1486.5 (4.8)	1470	-
ν_4 (N-O stretch)	1061.3 (331)	1031	853.1/850.2
ν_5 (O-N-O bend)	721.6 (21)	718.7	-
ν_6 (N-O-H out-of-plane wagging)	687 (221)	665	638.4
B ₂ O ₂			
ν_1 (B ₂ O ₂ symmetric stretch)	2254 (0)	2212.0 (0.7)	2060
ν_2 (B ₂ O ₂ asymmetric stretch)	2039 (348)	1957.3 (367.7)	1897.8
ν_3 (B-B stretch)	636 (0.0)	590.4 (0.7)	585.0
ν_4 (B=O/B=O twist)	544 (0.0)	491.2 (0.0)	410.0
ν_5 (O=B-B=O in-plane bending)	233 (95)	202.7 (19.7)	213.0
C ₂ N ₂			
ν_1 (C≡N/C≡N symmetric stretch)	2666 (0.0)	2661 (0.0)	2330
ν_2 (C≡N/C≡N asymmetric stretch)	2625 (9)	2610 (8)	2158
ν_3 (C-C stretch)	930 (18)	925 (18)	846
ν_4 (CN/CN in-plane bending)	649 (0)	640 (0)	503
ν_5 (CN/CN out-of-plane bending)	267 (17)	260 (9)	234

^aSee Ref. 41.

^bThe average scale factor ($\nu_{\text{exp}}/\nu_{\text{cal}}$) 0.8949.

Values in brackets are intensities (in) km mol⁻¹.

scale factor for the stretching and bending vibrations of the monomers are shown in the Table 7. The results included here, are detailed description of the normal modes of the monomers obtained from MP2/6-311G calculations. It can be seen from the results in Table 7, the calculated values of frequencies at the MP2 level are marginally in better agreement with the experimental data than calculated at SCF level.

It was of paramount importance to investigate the accuracy of the *ab initio* calculations at SCF levels and MP2 levels for the prediction of the infrared intensities. The close comparison between the predicted values of the infrared intensities for the vibrations of the monomers with the available experimental data, give a satisfactory and deformation vibrations.

The second step in the study was to predict the vibrational frequencies and infrared intensities for the hydrogen-bonded complexes B₂O₂-HONO(*trans*) (**1A**) and B₂O₂-HONO(*cis*) (**1B**), C₂N₂-HONO(*trans*) (**2A**) and C₂N₂-HONO(*cis*) (**2B**) and to estimate the changes in the vibrational characteristics arising from the hydrogen bonding. The predicted results for the complexes **1A** and **1B** are given in Tables 8 and 9. It can be seen from the results, that most of the intermolecular vibrations of the dimers can be correlated with the normal modes of the monomers, described in Table 7.

The hydrogen bonding leads to the changes in the localized modes to each normal mode in the monomers. In addition, there are three more intermolecular vibrations

Table 8. Calculated vibrational frequencies (cm⁻¹) for HONO-(*cis*)-B₂O₂ complex obtained from HF/6-311G and MP2 calculations

Mode	HF	MP2
ν_1 (O-H stretch)	3777.5 (631.7)	3692 (6.39)
ν_2 (O=B/B=O symmetric stretch)	2250.8 (0.5)	2204 (0.9)
ν_3 (OB/OB asymmetric stretch)	2036.9 (426)	1998 (4.19)
ν_4 (HONO out-of-plane (swinging))	1805 (207)	1779 (200)
ν_5 (HONO out-of-plane (wagging))	1541 (17)	1507 (22)
ν_6 (N-O stretch)	1116.5 (338)	1082 (3.49)
ν_7 (HONO twisting)	881 (234)	809 (2.10)
ν_8 (ONO bending (in-plane))	743 (29)	694 (20)
ν_9 (B-B stretch)	639.8 (3.6)	597 (3.9)
ν_{10} (B=O/B=O bending (out-of-plane))	542.5 (0.06)	513 (0.10)
ν_{11} (B ₂ O ₂ /HONO bending (out-of-plane))	269.4 (0.7)	232 (0.7)
ν_{12} (B ₂ O ₂ (wagging) + HONO bending (in-plane))	243.8 (88)	213 (8.3)
ν_{13} (HONO-O bending)	182.5 (9.6)	159 (9.1)

Values in brackets are intensities (in) km mol⁻¹.

(ν_{12} - ν_{14}) which arise from the complexation between nitrous acid and B₂O₂: the wagging B₂O₂/HONO, the O-HONO in-plane and out-of-plane bending vibrations.

The predicted values of the stretching O₅-H₄ vibration for the B₂O₂-HONO(*trans*) complex (Table 8) are in the

range 140–182.5 cm⁻¹ with weak infrared intensity. The O₃-H₄ stretching frequency value in HONO-*trans* show a decrease during hydrogen bond complexation by 110 cm⁻¹ at SCF level, likewise B-O/B-O symmetric stretch also show a decrease in the vibrational frequency value from

Table 9. Calculated vibrational frequencies (cm⁻¹) for HONO-(*trans*)-B₂O₂ complex obtained from HF/6-311G and MP2 calculations

Mode	HF	MP2
ν_1 (O-H stretch)	3948 (403)	3889 (392)
ν_2 (B=O/B=O symmetric stretch)	2250 (0.5)	2205 (0.7)
ν_3 (B=O/B=O asymmetric stretch)	2028 (392)	2007 (381)
ν_4 (N=O stretch HONO out-of-plane swinging)	1879 (144)	1850 (144)
ν_5 (NOH + NO stretch/bending)	1523.2 (251)	1501 (243)
ν_6 (NOH out-of-plane bending)	1061.6 (204)	1032 (210)
ν_7 (OH...O wagging)	785.9 (209)	753 (199)
ν_8 (O=N-O bending (in-plane))	773.0 (9)	742 (12)
ν_9 (B-B stretch)	636.8 (1.3)	616 (2.1)
ν_{10} (B ₂ O ₂ bending (in-plane))	548 (0.03)	531 (0.7)
ν_{11} (B ₂ O ₂ bending (out-of-plane))	543 (3.3)	528 (4.7)
ν_{12} (B ₂ O ₂ (wagging) + HONO bending)	248 (110)	229 (117)
ν_{13} (O=N-O wagging)	217 (5)	200 (7)
ν_{14} (O...H stretch)	165 (8)	155 (9)
ν_{15} (B ₂ O ₂ /HONO bending (out-of-plane))	104 (5)	90 (8)
ν_{16} (HONO bending (out-of-plane))	21 (2.3)	17 (2.9)

Values in brackets are intensities (in) km mol⁻¹.

monomer to complexation. Similarly stretching shift in O_3-H_4 by 108 cm^{-1} is also observed in HONO-*cis* during complexation at SCF level (see Table 9).

In parallel to HONO- B_2O_2 complexation, we carried out the computation of vibrational frequencies and infrared intensities of HONO(*cis/trans*)- C_2N_2 complexes. The results are reported in Tables 10 and 11.

It can be seen from the results that O_3-H_4 symmetric stretch vibrational value show a decrease by 70 cm^{-1} in HONO-*trans*- C_2N_2 complexation with respect to free HONO-*trans* molecule (see Table 10). But in the case of O_3-H_4 symmetric stretch of HONO-*cis* show also decrease

in the value by 48 cm^{-1} in during HONO-*cis*- C_2N_2 complexation, which is less than its *trans*-complex (see Table 11). These comparisons of the frequency shifts alongwith the corresponding values further show that the HONO-*trans* H-bonded complexes with B_2O_2 and C_2N_2 are stronger than their corresponding HONO-*cis* complexes. In a nutshell, it is established that the hydrogen bonding leads to the substantial change in the vibrational characteristics for the monomer bonds participating in the hydrogen bonding. For the complexes B_2O_2 -HONO-*(trans)* (1A), B_2O_2 -HONO-*(cis)* (1B), C_2N_2 -HONO-*(trans)* (2A) and C_2N_2 -HONO-*(cis)* (2B), the stretching of O-H (ν_1) and the deformation $\nu(\text{HONO})$ vibrations are more sensitive. The *ab initio* and HF-LYP calculations show that the torsional HONO vibrations (ν_5) in the complexes, is shifted to higher frequencies.

Conclusions :

The main results of the present study are :

- (i) The bond lengths and angles for the complexes $B_2O_2/\text{HONO}(\textit{cis/trans})$ and $C_2N_2/\text{HONO}(\textit{cis/trans})$ are slightly perturbed from their values in the monomers. The more sensitive to the complexations are the structural parameters of HONO-*trans* than HONO-*cis*.
- (ii) The charge rearrangement upon hydrogen bonding for HONO-*trans* is more significant than HONO-*cis*.

Table 10. Calculated vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) for HONO-*(trans)*- C_2N_2 complex obtained from HF/6-311G and MP2 calculations

Mode	HF	MP2
ν_1 (O-H stretch)	3986.7 (764)	3981 (767)
ν_2 (C=N/C=N symmetric stretch)	2676 (7.5)	2670 (7)
ν_3 (C=N/C=N asymmetric stretch)	2435.6 (15)	2422 (15)
ν_4 (N=O stretch)	1880.5 (141)	1872 (143)
ν_5 (HON (bending) + N=O stretch)	1496.6 (306)	1498 (210)
ν_6 (N-O stretch)	1056.6 (204)	1059 (250)
ν_7 (C-C stretch)	933 (5.3)	929 (5)
ν_8 (ONO bending (in-plane))	770.2 (5.3)	771 (5)
ν_9 (O-H wagging)	748.5 (183)	743 (190)
ν_{10} (N-C-C=N bending (in-plane))	652.4 (0.3)	652 (0.7)
ν_{11} (N-C-C=N bending (out-of-plane))	278.5 (13.8)	270 (14)

Values in brackets are intensities (in) km mol^{-1} .

Table 11. Calculated vibrational frequencies (cm⁻¹) for HONO(*cis*)-C₂N₂ complex obtained from HF/6-311G and MP2 calculations

Mode	HF	MP2
ν_1 (O-H stretch)	3837.4 (272)	3826 (280)
ν_2 (C=N/C=N symmetric stretch)	2675 (7)	2671 (8)
ν_3 (C=N/C=N asymmetric stretch)	2433 (16)	2429 (17)
ν_4 (N=O stretch)	1806 (192)	1801 (195)
ν_5 (HONO bending (in-plane))	1512 (0.6)	1501 (0.9)
ν_6 (N-O stretch)	1094 (306)	1089 (301)
ν_7 (C-C stretch)	935 (0.6)	939 (0.7)
ν_8 (O-H wagging)	787 (218)	781 (218)
ν_9 (O=N-O bending (in-plane))	731 (19)	721 (19)
ν_{10} (C ₂ N ₂ bending (in-plane))	652 (0.0)	645 (0)
ν_{11} (C ₂ N ₂ bending (out-of-plane))	275 (16)	267 (18)
ν_{12} (N-H/ONO wagging)	157 (5)	150 (7)

Values in brackets are intensities (in) km mol⁻¹.

(iii) The *ab initio* calculations at SCF level predict that the *trans*-HONO/B₂O₂ and *trans*-HONO/C₂N₂ complexes are more stable than their HONO-*cis* complexes.

(iv) The comparison between the predicted values of the infrared intensities for the vibrations of the monomers with the available experimental data show that the calculations used in the study give a satisfactory description of the intensities for the stretching and deformation vibrations.

(v) In the summary, one can conclude that the high level quantum-chemical calculations may be highly successful in reproducing the experimental values.

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